

Complexing behaviour of 4-vanillideneamino-3-methyl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole towards Ag^{I} , Tl^{I} , Zn^{II} , Pb^{II} , Cd^{II} , Hg^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Pd^{II} , Rh^{III} and Ir^{III}

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The complexes of Ag^{I} , Tl^{I} , Zn^{II} , Pb^{II} , Cd^{II} , Hg^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Pd^{II} , Rh^{III} and Ir^{III} with 4-vanillideneamino-3-methyl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole have been synthesised. Octahedral structure has been proposed for the Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Rh^{III} and Ir^{III} complexes, square-planar structure for the Pd^{II} complex, tetrahedral structure for the Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} complexes and linear polymeric structure for the Tl^{I} and Ag^{I} complexes.

The present communication discusses the synthesis and characterization of complexes of Ag^{I} , Tl^{I} , Zn^{II} , Pb^{II} , Cd^{II} , Hg^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Pd^{II} , Rh^{III} and Ir^{III} with the Schiff base ligand 4-vanillideneamino-3-methyl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole (VAMMT or LH).

Results and Discussion

Elemental analysis data indicate the stoichiometry : $\text{M}(\text{L})$ for $\text{M} = \text{Ag}^{\text{I}}$ and Tl^{I} ; $\text{M}(\text{L})_2$ for $\text{M} = \text{Zn}^{\text{II}}$, Hg^{II} , Pb^{II} and Pd^{II} ; $\text{M}(\text{L})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ for $\text{M} = \text{Co}^{\text{II}}$ and Ni^{II} and $\text{M}(\text{L})_3$ for $\text{M} = \text{Rh}^{\text{III}}$ and Ir^{III} .

The magnetic moment (3.12 B.M.) of the Ni^{II} complex of VAMMT at room temperature is in agreement with those reported for octahedral nickel(II) complexes¹. The reason for slightly higher observed value than that expected may be due to the orbital contributions^{2,3}. The high value of magnetic moment (4.98 B.M.) of the cobalt-VAMMT complex at room temperature arises from the high degree of orbital contribution for octahedral Co^{II} due to the three-fold degeneracy of ${}^4T_{1g}$ ground state^{3,4}. The magnetic susceptibility studies show that all the complexes, excepting Ni^{II} and Co^{II} are diamagnetic.

The loss in weight by 5.71% (calc. 5.79%) of the Ni^{II} and Co^{II} complexes at 90–225° corresponds to loss of two molecules of coordinated water. A sharp decrease in weight is observed in the thermograms of these complexes in the temperature range 250–550° due to the oxidation of

the organic ligand and formation of the metal oxides. All the other complexes are stable upto 200° and decompose in two major steps, the final products at 600–800° being the metal oxides.

Low molar conductance values ($2.5\text{--}30.8 \Omega^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^2$) of these complexes indicate their non-electrolytic nature.

The electronic bands observed at 18622, 19802 and 23094 cm^{-1} for Ir^{III} complex and at 16638, 19417 and 22321 cm^{-1} for the Rh^{III} complex ions are due to the transitions ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}$, ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1T_{1g}$ and ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1T_{2g}$ respectively. The values of crystal field stabilisation energy ($10 Dq$), Racah parameter (B) and the covalency factor (β) have been evaluated are in conformity with that of other Ir^{III} and Rh^{III} complexes with similar donors.

IR spectra of the ligands reveal bands at 3100–3000 (N-H) and 2900 cm^{-1} (C-H). It is reasonable to expect deprotonation of the ligand molecules before complexation. After deprotonation, the ligand units can link with the metal ion at either N or S end of the thioamide group. The ligand bands at 1630 and 1590 cm^{-1} are assigned to $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ of the azomethine linkage⁵. Slight shift of this band to lower wavenumber in the complexes indicates the coordination of the nitrogen of this group with the metal ions.

Some new bands are also observed in the spectra of the complexes due to $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$, $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M-S}}$ coupled with other modes of vibrations of the ligand molecules. Bands due to coordinated water are also observed in the spectra of the Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes around 3500 and 890 cm^{-1} . These results indicate that the ligand chelates metal ions through

Note

the deprotonated thiol sulfur and nitrogen atom of the azomethine linkage in VAMMT.

Experimental

The chemicals used were all of AnalaR or chemically pure grade. The ligand (VAMMT) was synthesized by condensing 3-methyl-4-amino-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole⁶ with vanillin, m.p. 222–223°. The complexes were prepared by refluxing the respective metal chlorides/nitrates/acetates (0.01 mol) and the ligand (0.01/0.02/0.03 mol) in ethanol (75 ml) for 2–3 h. The solid complexes were washed with hot water, warm ethanol and ether and dried at 110–130°. The complexes gave satisfactory elemental analyses.

Magnetic susceptibility was determined with a Gouy balance at room temperature. Thermogravimetric analysis was carried out on a Mettler TA 4000 thermal analyzer in air at the rate of 10°/min upto 800° at Department of

Chemical Engineering, K.R.E.C., Suratkal. The molar conductivities of the complexes in 1×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³ DMF solution were measured with an Elico conductivity meter. The absorption spectra (DMF) were recorded on a Beckman DU-6 spectrophotometer and IR spectra (KBr/CsI) on a Perkin-Elmer 1330 spectrophotometer.

References

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